

DIHNET.EU
Europe's Network of Digital Innovation Hubs

D1.3: Communication material for policy makers

Grant Agreement Number	825640
Project Acronym	DIHNET.EU
Deliverable Date	29 November 2019
Authors	Maurits Butter (TNO), Kristina Karanikolova (TNO), Govert Gijsbers (TNO)
Number of Pages	76
Number of Annexes	0
Version	2
Reviewed by	Marta Palau Franco (euRobotics)
Approved by	Maurits Butter (TNO)
Dissemination level	Public

DIHNET.EU

Europe's Network of Digital Innovation Hubs

Digital Innovation Hubs and Networks

A primer for policy makers

Purpose of the presentation

Provide an easy to read overview of development of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and networks of hubs

- ▶ Highlight the most important policy issues for decision makers
- ▶ Aimed at policy makers at different levels: regional, national, international

Presentation overview

- ▶ Why DIH?
 - ▶ The challenge of digitisation
- ▶ DIH concepts and content:
 - ▶ Structure
 - ▶ Functions
 - ▶ DIH as a one-stop-shop
 - ▶ DIH services
- ▶ DIH evolution
 - ▶ From single hubs to networks
 - ▶ Policies for future
- ▶ Key issues for Policy Makers
 - ▶ DIH sustainability
 - ▶ Financing DIHs and networks
 - ▶ Skills for DIHs
 - ▶ DIHs and specialisation
 - ▶ Dealing with multiple DIH initiatives
 - ▶ Building DIH networks: governance, priorities, business models sustainability
 - ▶ Front runners and left behind regions
 - ▶ Cross border collaboration

Why are DIHs important?

The Challenge of Digitisation

The Challenge of digitization

- ▶ Technologies such as AI, data analytics, cloud, HPC, cybersecurity offer opportunities to improve our everyday life and transform industry.
- ▶ Europe needs to widely adopt these technologies in order to preserve its competitive position.

CHALLENGES:

There are still big differences in the level of digitalisation of industry across sectors, Member States and regions.

Only 1 out of 5 companies across the EU are highly digitised.

Around 60% of large industries and more than 90% of SMEs feel lagging behind in digital innovation.

Europe is lagging behind on online platforms, EU industry cannot afford losing leadership in digital industrial platforms.

90% of future jobs will require some level of digital skills while 44% of Europeans lack basic digital skills.

OPPORTUNITIES:

Digitalisation of products and services can add more than **€110 billion of annual revenue** for industry in Europe until 2020.

Background: Digitising European Industry initiative (DEI)

- ▶ To support the benefits of digitisation, already in 2016, the Commission invested €500 million in Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) to “help ensure that every company, small or large, high-tech or not, can grasp the digital opportunities”.

Figure: Pillars of the Digitising European Industry initiative
Source: [European Commission, 2018](#)

What are the benefits of DIHs?

- ▶ Promoting collaboration in the ecosystem to support the sharing and combining reduces risks
- ▶ Lowering costs and increases the expertise
- ▶ Connecting research/technology to business application
- ▶ Creating and maintains a dynamic regional ecosystem
 - ▶ This helps the sustainability of the shared facility
 - ▶ Increases the awareness and competitiveness of the regional industry
- ▶ Bringing together different mindsets among:
 - ▶ Scientists, researchers, engineers, business developers and entrepreneurs

Source: TNO

What are Digital Innovation Hubs?

The concept of a DIH

Digital Innovation Hubs: key characteristics

- ▶ Digital Innovation Hubs are multi-partner networks aiming to support companies in their digital transformation
- ▶ Digital innovation hubs:
 - ▶ Focus on *regional* companies, and SMEs and mid-caps in particular
 - ▶ Support SMEs to cross the valley of death by combining technological, business, and ecosystem services
 - ▶ Focus on one technology and/or market domain
 - ▶ Are embedded in the regional ecosystem
 - ▶ Offer shared expertise and infrastructure available among partners
 - ▶ Supporting (Semi) open innovation

Digital Innovation Hubs are multi-partner networks

Often seen partners

- ▶ Competence centers
 - ▶ Research and Technology Organisations
 - ▶ Academic universities
- ▶ Cluster/network organisations
- ▶ Regional development agencies
- ▶ Regional authorities
- ▶ Incubator/accelerator organisations
- ▶ Industry (vendors, consultants)

Other partners

- ▶ Vocational education institution, Universities of applied science
- ▶ Private financial institutions (e.g., VC, private bank)
- ▶ Industry associations
- ▶ Real estate agents
- ▶ Large enterprises

DIHs: One-stop-shop for SMEs

- ▶ DIHs are a one-stop-shop for SMEs and mid-caps:
 - ▶ Providing SMEs with business and technology and market support
 - ▶ Developing and providing access to the regional ecosystem
 - ▶ Offering trainings and skills development programs
- ▶ DIHs offer support to companies at a “working distance” (in the region)

Figure: Four Functions of Digital Innovation Hubs
Source: [European Commission, 2019](#)

DIHs: customer groups

- ▶ DIHs address different types of clients with different needs. This requires a DIH to offer a broad service portfolio.
- ▶ It is crucial that DIHs offer a combination of ecosystem, business and technology services in order to support each of these customer groups

DIH defined by their services

- ▶ Digital Innovation Hubs are best described by their functions: the services they offer
- ▶ Three main types of services can be distinguished:
 - ▶ Ecosystem development services
 - ▶ Technology development services
 - ▶ Business and market-oriented services
- ▶ Skills and training is a horizontal service that can touch upon any of the other three services
- ▶ Variations and service portfolio are heavily dependent on regional/local needs

DIHs: Technology services

- ▶ Technology services are often offered by the participating Competence Centers and often form the core of the DIHs activities.
- ▶ These can relate both to the active development of projects or more broadly to provide demonstrators and testing support to companies.
- ▶ Trainings can be provided on opportunities that technologies offer, but also on how to operate the technologies, program, etc.
- ▶ Opportunities also exist in collaborating with universities or institutes for vocational training to develop future education and traineeship programmes

<i>Services</i>		<i>Activities</i>	
technology	Strategic RDI	Training and education	Joint, pre-competitive R&D, secondment from companies
	Contract research		Specific R&D, technology concept development, proof of concept
	Technical support on scale-up		Concept validation, prototyping, small series production
	Provision of tech infrastructure		Renting equipment, low rate production, platform technology infrastructure, Lab facilities
	Testing and validation		Certification, product demonstration, product qualification

DIHs: Business support services

- ▶ Connecting business support services and technological services is where DIHs can add value to SMEs and can multiply their impact.
- ▶ DIHs can support SMEs in developing business models that will generate revenues profit for SMEs, as well as offering support with finding financing, market intelligence and even project proposal writing and management
- ▶ Trainings can be provided on developing business models for different entities - from start-ups to incumbents which need to re-organise their business entirely.
- ▶ Trainings on how to approach different financing institutions and what (investors) language and (state-aid) rules are other possible training and skills activities

<i>Services</i>		<i>Activities</i>	
<i>business</i>	Incubator/accelerator support	<i>Training and education</i>	Voice-Of-Customer, market assessment, business development, legal. IPR, location, sales strategy
	Access to finance		Financial engineering, connection to funding sources, investment plans
	Project development		Identification of opportunities, creating consortia, development of proposals
	Offering housing		Office space and space for experimentation and pilot manufacturing

DIHs: Ecosystem services

- ▶ Ecosystem development services are key to raise awareness about digital opportunities and activate the regional ecosystem
- ▶ These services develop interest in the ecosystem, creating a funnel through which already existing SMEs are further activated and supported with other services while new companies are attracted to the hub's ecosystem
- ▶ DIHs need to develop their own capacities in community building, strategy development, lobbying, etc. They should also develop capacities to collaborate with other hubs and networks.

<i>Services</i>		<i>Activities</i>	
ecosystem	Community building	Scouting, brokerage, awareness creation, dissemination, ecosystem building	
	Strategy development	Market intelligence, market assessments, road-mapping, technology watch	
	Ecosystem learning	Workshops, seminars to share knowledge and experience	
	Representation, promotion	Representing interests during meetings & conferences, organising (country) visits, roadshows	
	Training for the DIH and the ecosystem		

Combining a full set of services is key to sustainability

Services		Source: TNO	Activities
ecosystem	Community building	Skills training, education	Scouting, brokerage, awareness creation, dissemination, ecosystem building
	Strategy development		Market intelligence, market assessments, road-mapping, technology watch
	Ecosystem learning		Workshops, seminars to share knowledge and experience
	Representation, promotion		Representing interests during meetings & conferences, organising (country) visits, roadshows
technology	Strategic RDI		Joint, pre-competitive R&D, secondment from companies
	Contract research		Specific R&D, technology concept development, proof of concept
	Technical support on scale-up		Concept validation, prototyping, small series production
	Provision of tech infrastructure		Renting equipment, low rate production, platform technology infrastructure, Lab facilities
	Testing and validation		Certification, product demonstration, product qualification
business	Incubator/accelerator support		Voice-Of-Customer, market assessment, business development, legal. IPR, location, sales strategy
	Access to finance		Financial engineering, connection to funding sources, investment plans
	Project development		Identification of opportunities, creating consortia, development of proposals
	Offering housing	Office space and space for experimentation and pilot manufacturing	

Specialised courses on ecosystem/technology/business, strategy development on topic education

Digital Innovation Hubs Evolution

DIHs movement - a success story

- ▶ More than 520 Digital Innovation Hubs are currently registered in the JRC DIH Catalogue
- ▶ Many Member States have DIH representation

DIH concept adopted in national policies

Countries across the EU have adopted policies supporting the digitisation of industry

DIH evolution: single hubs to networks

- ▶ The concept of a DIH has evolved in the last years, spreading among EU member states and further developing into various organisational forms. Based on the Competence Centers and DIHs, regional and European networks have emerged. A number of different initiatives on EU level have also been supported.
- ▶ At least four general types of entities can be distinguished, each with specific function, services and focus

The role of Competence Centers (CC)

- ▶ Competence Centers often are internationally oriented centers of expertise, supporting companies in translating research into application technologies and innovations.
- ▶ CC offer:
 - ▶ access to technological infrastructure and the associated knowhow
 - ▶ access to testing and experimentation environments
 - ▶ access to demonstrators and showcases of digital technologies
- ▶ Competence Centers are usually highly specialised in a particular (set of) technologies.
- ▶ Competence centers often are part of a Research and Technology Organisations (Fraunhofer (DE), VTT (FI), TNO (NL) or Universities).

The role of Digital Innovation Hubs

- ▶ Digital Innovation Hubs often focus on one technology and/or market domain
- ▶ Support regional SMEs to cross the valley of death by combining technological, business, financial and ecosystem support services
- ▶ DIHs are multi-partner initiatives, connecting and building on existing competence centers, clusters and platforms in the region

The role of Regional DIH Networks

- ▶ Regional DIH Networks are regionally oriented entities, often initiated or supported by a regional development agency.
- ▶ They support:
 - ▶ Regional ecosystem development
 - ▶ Coordination multiple DIH nodes
 - ▶ Benefit from Economy of scale
 - ▶ Multi tech/market domain focus
 - ▶ Implementing Smart specialisation and pan-EU collaboration
- ▶ Examples are the 5 regional DIHs in the Netherlands which support more than 40 field-labs (see the Smart Industry [website](#))

The role of pan-EU networks

- ▶ These networks aim to:
 - ▶ Initiate pan-EU collaboration and Smart Specialisation
 - ▶ One tech/market domain focus
 - ▶ Facilitate regional learning via multi-national, open innovation partnership
 - ▶ Creating EU awareness on new topics
- ▶ Examples include European H2020 projects such as DIHNET, RODIN, SmartAgriHubs
 - › As well as existing networks such as EEN, Specialisation platform partnership

Why is pan-EU collaboration important?

Strengthen EU leadership and create a sound industrial technology base that can compete on high level with other global regions

1. Trans-regional collaboration in R&D&I to make **better use of existing research**;
2. The **efficiency and effectiveness of translating** technologies into business, time to access
3. **Increased shared use of expertise**, looking at importing/exporting knowledge;
4. Pan-EU industrial value chains to **use existing European industrial partners**
5. **Exchange experience** on how to efficiently and effectively run DIHs;
6. **Alignment of national and regional funding** on a pan-EU level, reducing duplication and increasing its impact;

Each of these initiatives offers different services and added value

Service CC	Service DIH node	Service reg. DIH network	Services pan EU network
Community building	Community building	Community building	EU market place
Strategy development	Strategy development	Strategy development	EU awareness creation
Ecosystem learning	Ecosystem learning	Ecosystem learning	EU strategy development
Representation, promotion	Representation, promotion	Representation, promotion	Representation on EU level
Strategic RDI	Strategic RDI	Strategic RDI	EU widening and sharing expertise
Contract research	Contract research	Contract research	Creating common approaches
Technical support on scale-up	Technical support on scale-up	Technical support on scale-up	Pan-EU collaborative research
Provision of technology infrastructure	Provision of technology infrastructure	Provision of technology infrastructure	Standardization
Testing and validation	Testing and validation	Testing and validation	Smart(er) specialization
Incubator/accelerator support	Incubator/accelerator support	Incubator/accelerator support	Pan-EU value chain creation
Access to finance	Access to finance	Access to finance	EU industry market assessment
Skills and education	Skills and education	Skills and education	Pan-EU innovation fund
Project development	Project development	Project development	Organizing trans-regional collaboration
Offering housing	Offering housing	Offering housing	
		Pan-EU Collaboration	

Skills training, education

Skills training, education

Skills training, education

Joint skills development

Different initiatives exist in a complex and dynamic ecosystem

Source: TNO, 2019

And the ecosystem is still growing...

- ▶ This requires coordination and collaboration among existing networks, policy levels and among sectors.

Policies for the future: Digital Europe Programme (DEP)

- ▶ European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) will be central in the Digital Europe Programme.
- ▶ Digital Europe Programme aims to build strategic digital capacities and support the wide deployment of digital technologies in EU industry.
- ▶ A total budget of €9.2 billion is planned

Figure: Digital Europe Programme for DIHs
(Source: [European Commission, 2018](#).)

Policies for the future: Digital Europe Programme (DEP)

- ▶ European Digital Innovation Hubs are expected to:
 - ▶ Stimulate the adoption of AI, HPC, and Cybersecurity in EU industry
 - ▶ Support both local and European functions
 - ▶ Establish a strong collaboration network of EDIHs
 - ▶ Receive co-financing by EU and national/regional funds

Figure: Digital Europe Programme for DIHs
(Source: [European Commission, 2019](#).)

Policies for the future: complementarities among upcoming funding programmes

- ▶ The DEP program and DIHs will be closely connected to other funding instruments in Europe.

Figure: Complementarities among European Programmes supporting DIHs (Source: [European Commission, 2018](#).)

Figure: Digital Europe Programme for DIHs (Source: [European Commission, 2018](#).)

Key issues for Policy Makers

Sustainability for DIHs and regional DIH networks

DIH sustainability

- ▶ DIHs address complex problems (e.g. in health care, climate change)
 - ▶ Collaboration among various stakeholders is needed but is challenging
- ▶ DIHs have a societal mission and provide a mix of public and private services
 - ▶ Often, long-term public funding, combined with multiple business models for the DIH are needed for ensuring the sustainability of the hub and its focus on solving market failures (societal mission)
- ▶ Ecosystem development is often key function of a DIH
 - ▶ This implies high indirect costs

Creating and capturing value to ensure DIH sustainability

Creating Value

- ▶ Digital Innovation Hubs address public and private actors in the ecosystem. In order to respond to different needs, DIHs have to create value by:
 - ▶ Providing a **full set of services** (addressing technological, business and ecosystem activities) to the ecosystem
 - ▶ Connecting the different mindsets
 - ▶ Addressing market failures to help public authorities

Capturing Value

- ▶ DIHs need to combine public and private funding in order to develop a sustainable business model:
 - ▶ Public funding is essential to cover the basic expenses of a hub. DIHs are fundamentally different from companies as they address market failures and serve a societal mission. Consequently DIHs need to utilise public funding from regional, national and EU level while respecting state aid rules
 - ▶ Private and in-kind funding from partners
 - ▶ Private income is generated directly by customers (via memberships, pay per services, etc).

Government: Interest and willingness to pay

- ▶ DIHs often need to combine different types of public funding instruments.
- ▶ Public authorities have different objectives and are willing to financially support for (only some) of the services offered.
- ▶ DIHs need to ensure they understand the motivation of different governance levels to support a DIH initiative

Regional

Community building	€
Strategy development	€
Ecosystem learning	€
Representation, promotion	
Strategic RDI	€
Contract research	€
Technical support on scale-up	€
Provision of technology infra	€
Testing and validation	€
Incubator/accelerator support	€
Access to finance	€
Skills and education	€
Project development	€
Offering housing	€

National

Community building	
Strategy development	€
Ecosystem learning	
Representation, promotion	
Strategic RDI	€
Contract research	€
Technical support on scale-up	€
Provision of technology infra	
Testing and validation	
Incubator/accelerator support	€
Access to finance	€
Skills and education	€
Project development	
Offering housing	

European H2020

Community building	€
Strategy development	€
Ecosystem learning	€
Representation, promotion	
Strategic RDI	€
Contract research	
Technical support on scale-up	
Provision of technology infra	
Testing and validation	
Incubator/accelerator support	
Access to finance	
Skills and education	
Project development	
Offering housing	

Industry: Interest and willingness to pay

- ▶ DIHs serve different industry players.
- ▶ Depending on their maturity and size, different companies would be interested and able to pay for different services.

Large companies

Community building	
Strategy development	
Ecosystem learning	
Representation, promotion	
Strategic RDI	€
Contract research	€€
Technical support on scale-up	€€
Provision of technology infra	€€
Testing and validation	€€
Incubator/accelerator support	
Access to finance	
Skills and education	
Project development	€
Offering housing	

SMEs

Community building	
Strategy development	
Ecosystem learning	
Representation, promotion	
Strategic RDI	
Contract research	€€
Technical support on scale-up	€
Provision of technology infra	€
Testing and validation	€€
Incubator/accelerator support	€
Access to finance	
Skills and education	€
Project development	
Offering housing	

Start-ups

Community building	
Strategy development	
Ecosystem learning	
Representation, promotion	
Strategic RDI	
Contract research	€
Technical support on scale-up	€
Provision of technology infra	€
Testing and validation	€
Incubator/accelerator support	
Access to finance	
Skills and education	
Project development	
Offering housing	

Financing a DIH is a patchwork

- ▶ Long term sustainability of a hub requires continuous public funding support.

Source: XS2 I4MS, EU-Great!, 2017

Different services require separate business models

- ▶ Business Models describe how DIHs create value from their services.
- ▶ In order to ensure the long-term functioning of the hub, a mix of business models for each service is needed.
- ▶ Key elements of the business model are how, who, what and why services are offered.

Sustainability and business models for pan-EU networks

Sustainability and business models for pan-EU networks

- ▶ Business models and sustainability for pan-EU collaboration differ significantly from those for individual DIHs

Business models are about...

- ▶ Describing the core logic of the initiative through which it creates and captures value within its ecosystem
- ▶ To structurally explore the business models for pan-EU networks, the business model navigator is suggested.

Elements of the Business model navigator: the 'What'

Possible pan-EU network activities

Mentoring programme, EU skills strategy development, EU skills summer school

Elements of the Business model navigator: the 'Who'

A set of customer types for networks

- ▶ The DIHs and Competence Centres:
 - ▶ Supporting finding customers, RDI partners, finance
- ▶ Regional (and national) authorities
 - ▶ Improving competitiveness for their industry/research, creating export opportunities and increasing impact of public RDI expenditures
- ▶ SMEs
 - ▶ Access to capabilities outside of their region (industry/research), access to finance
- ▶ The European Commission
 - ▶ Improving the interregional collaboration and proving the value of the European project
- ▶ Vendor based manufacturing industry
 - ▶ Enhancing their access to the demand side of the European market and supply of technologies

Elements of the Business model navigator: the 'How'

Key assets for pan-EU networks and Public private partnerships

- ▶ The EU-fund for interregional collaboration
- ▶ Overview of the existing infrastructure and technological expertise
- ▶ Easy access to infrastructure and technological expertise
- ▶ Experience in brokerage and value chain creation
- ▶ Strength to mobilize the European ecosystem
- ▶ Use cases for pan-EU collaboration
- ▶ Specific information on the domain, actors, technology, business
- ▶ Insight in the European ecosystem stakeholders
- ▶ Direct contacts with all stakeholders, on various levels
- ▶ The brand: known to the community, with trustworthiness and members

Key network partners in pan-EU networks

- ▶ An orchestrator for network management
- ▶ Partner taking care of the fund
- ▶ Partners for brokerage
- ▶ Communication/branding partner
- ▶ Regional representation for the regional connections
- ▶ Investors to create the fund
- ▶ Access to CCs/DIHs to provide services
- ▶ Adding value via international coverage

Elements of the Business model navigator: the 'Why'

Perhaps the most important, but hard to address

Why does it generate profit

Different users would be interested in and willing to pay for different services

	<i>services</i> <small>© TNO 2019</small>	DIH/CC	Reg/Nat	SMEs	Vendor	EC
ecosystem	EU market place	++	++	+	++	++
	EU awareness creation		++			++
	EU strategy development	++	++			++
	Representation on EU level	++	++			
	EU widening and sharing expertise		++			++
technology	Creating common approaches	+	++			+
	Pan-EU collaborative research	++				++
	Standardization				++	
	Smart(er) specialization		++			++
business	Pan-EU value chain creation	+	+	++	++	
	EU industry market assessment	+	+	+	+	
	Pan-EU innovation fund	++		++		
	Organizing trans-regional collaboration	++	++		+	++
	Joint skills development	++	+	+		++

Skills for DIH and DIH networks

The need for (digital) skills

- ▶ Digitisation has reshaped the demand for skills among the workforce.
- ▶ Providing support for the development of (advanced) digital skills and provision of trainings is one of the key functions of a hub

The Skills Pyramid: from Hubs to SMEs

- ▶ The skills needed at each level are very different, but an integrated approach to skills development needs to address all levels

Source: TNO

Skills for SMEs

- ▶ In their digital transformation, SMEs need to develop new skills.
- ▶ These can relate to specific technologies, data analysis, ICT skills, but also management and business development skills to help them cope with the quickly changing environment

Skills for coaches and intermediaries to reach the early majority

- ▶ SMEs form the backbone of EU industry. To reach all these enterprises across sectors, a large multiplier is needed.
- ▶ This requires intermediaries who train trainers and provide coaching services, thus generating further impact
- ▶ DIHs play a key role in orchestrating skills development in the regions by:
 - ▶ Coordinating and facilitating skills provision by the DIHs, educational institutions, tech transfer offices
 - ▶ Supporting peer learning from front-runners
 - ▶ Ensuring that a blend of technology, business trainings are offered in mixed modes (formal training, traineeships, online, etc.)

Source: I4MS

Skills as a service by the DIH

- ▶ Technical skills
- ▶ Business skills
- ▶ Soft skills such as entrepreneurship, cultural differences, addressing different funding bodies
- ▶ DIHs can use different modalities to offer trainings:
 - ▶ Offering infrastructure for trainings
 - ▶ Establishment of specific workshops and training for (re)-skilling
 - ▶ Awareness campaigns for opportunities
 - ▶ Establish connection with educational institutes

Skills as service offered by DIHs: Building linkages with educational institutes

- ▶ In order to meet the future needs of industry, closer collaboration between industry and educational institutes is needed.
- ▶ DIHs can mediate and facilitate this collaboration at local level.
- ▶ Examples, such as the Brainport Industries Campus (NL), already exist

Source: [BIC, 2019](#)

Skills to establish and run the hub

- ▶ Trainings are needed to establish the capacities within the Hub
- ▶ Trainings and support to establish and run hubs are also needed. Examples are the I4MS Mentoring Programme.
- ▶ These need to be followed-up with further capacity building within the hubs themselves.

- Access to finance:
 - Webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jgHeNZQGsmw>.
 - Download the presentation [here](#).
- Building a Business Plan:
 - Webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ngvdPZ1Wsuk>.
 - Download the presentation [here](#).
- Business Models:
 - Webinar: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9ZI_56w9zJI.
 - Download the presentation [here](#).
- Ecosystem Assessment:
 - Webinar: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ddeKnZ3_P7I.
 - Download the presentation [here](#).
- Use cases:
 - No recording due to tech issues.
 - Download the presentation [here](#).
- Brokerage:
 - Webinar: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rUGFC7Vwk2w>.
 - Download the presentation [here](#).

Specialisation among various entities

The rationale for specialisation

- ▶ Better usage of the place-based characteristics of regions
- ▶ Improving the competitive advantage of Europe at large by:
 - ▶ Collaborating in R&D&I to make better use of existing research;
 - ▶ Increasing shared use of expertise and infrastructure, multi-partner use;
 - ▶ Aligning national and regional funding, reducing duplication and increasing its impact;

Different specialisation layers within the European landscape

Vertical Specialisation

- ▶ Within the region: Specialise between competitors within a region, aligning the capacities and optimising the use of public investments
- ▶ Interregional: Specialise between regions based on place-based available capacities
- ▶ Pan-EU: specialise among various networks and initiatives

Horizontal Specialisation

- ▶ Technology focus
- ▶ Sectorial Focus
- ▶ Within the value chain

Role of DIHs

- ▶ DIH are regionally oriented and therefore struggling with pan-EU specialisation
 - ▶ Specialising in a region is about sharing customers with competitors
- ▶ Specialisation is required especially on interregional level
 - ▶ Joining collaborations in more mission-oriented approaches
 - ▶ New business models needed for pan-EU collaborations
- ▶ The regions are pivotal to align capacities:
 - ▶ Get an overview of existing and needed capacities
 - ▶ Actively forge mission-based initiatives

Governance

Governance for DIHs

- ▶ It is about the key decisions that shape the DIH
- ▶ And the decisions that the DIH must make about its role in promoting (industrial) innovation
- ▶ It should address multi-level issues: local > regional > national > international

Governance among the different initiatives

- ▶ Clarification and division of responsibilities and activities among various EU initiatives is needed
- ▶ Specialisation among the different entities could strengthen collaboration

Dealing with multiple DIH initiatives

A large number of different initiatives are existing simultaneously

There is a
need for
coordination
and
improved
collaboration

New business models for
collaboration

Development of new smart
specialisation approaches for
collaboration between regions

Positioning of the European DIHs

Business models for cross-border services

- ▶ Further exploration of possible viable business models for collaboration among the different initiatives are needed
- ▶ One possibility for cross-regional collaboration is to use the regional DIH networks as project managers which facilitate the discussions and contact between SME and CC in different regions.

European DIHs (EDIHs)

Remaining policy considerations regarding to EDIHs:

- ▶ For EU policy-makers:
 - ▶ How to position EDIHs network within the overall EU landscape
 - ▶ How to ensure a spill-over effect of the capacities developed in EDIHs to other DIHs and networks
- ▶ For Member States:
 - ▶ How to select the nominated DIHs, especially in cases where many DIHs exist in a region and all are in line with EU KPIs.
- ▶ For regions:
 - ▶ How to distribute regional funding (especially ERDF) among the co-funding for EDIHs and the potential other DIHs
 - ▶ How to ensure economies of scale

Front runners vs. left-behind regions

- ▶ In recent years initiatives specifically targeting the development of DIHs in left-behind regions have been initiated (e.g. calls for DIHs in EU13)
- ▶ Especially with the EDIHs selection, a remaining challenge is:
 - ▶ How to ensure that left-behind regions are also addressed
 - ▶ How to raise and demand for digital services in these regions
 - ▶ How to level the playing field among already well-established DIHs and DIHs operating in a less efficient manner

DIHNET.EU
Europe's Network of Digital Innovation Hubs

Thank you

Website: www.dihnet.eu

E-mail: maurits.butter@tno.nl, ruud.baartmans@tno.nl